

Adducts of bis-(2-guanidiniumbenzimidazole) nickel (II) salts with pyridine and ammonia

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Adducts of bis-2-guanidiniumbenzimidazole nickel (II) salts with pyridine and ammonia have been studied. These are paramagnetic with $\mu = 2.98-3.05$ B.M. Octahedral configuration of the adducts has been confirmed from electronic absorption spectra. The spectrophotometric data for the pyridine adducts have been used to calculate the values for the parameters Δ , β and λ .

It has been observed that certain diamagnetic four-coordinated complexes of nickel (II) when dissolved in organic solvents of very different donor properties, become paramagnetic. French, *et al.*, suggested that the difference in stability between certain square planar and tetrahedral complexes is so small that under the influence of solvent molecules some square planar complexes are converted into tetrahedral complexes and thereby become paramagnetic.

Willis and Mellor¹ first reported the paramagnetism developed when some diamagnetic complexes of nickel (II) with salicylaldehyde derivatives were dissolved in organic solvents. They attributed this to an equilibrium between square and tetrahedral forms of the complexes in solution.

Development of solution paramagnetism has also been observed in the cases of diamagnetic nickel complexes with formyl camphor ethylenediamine, salicylaldehyde ortho-phenylenediamine, salicylaldimines, dimethylglyoxime and benzoylhydrazones^{2,3,4,5}. Magnetic moments vary from $0 < \mu < 3.2$ B.M. and thus do not conform to an integral number of electrons.

Electronic absorption spectra of nickel (II) complexes, with anomalous paramagnetism, do not show any convincing resemblance either in band position or in intensity to the tetrahedral species. The cause of paramagnetism due to conformational equilibrium¹ has therefore been discarded. At present it is generally accepted that the cause of the paramagnetism is due to decrease in the singlet triplet separation. According to Maki⁶ this is caused by an axial perturbation of the ligand field by the solvent molecules. According to the crystal field theory the tetrahedral arrangement of ligands around a paramagnetic nickel ion is also least preferred. The preference is for an octahedral environment because

1. H. S. French, M. Z. Magee and E. Sheffield, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 1924.
2. J. B. Willis and B. P. Mellor, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 1237.
3. F. Basolo and W. Matouh, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 5663.
4. H. G. Clark and A. L. Odell, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3431.
5. L. Sacconi Lombardo and P. Pasletti, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1958, **8**, 217.
6. G. Maki, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1958, **28**, 651, *ibid.*, 1959, **29**, 1129.

of larger crystal field stabilisation energy. Octahedral environment can be obtained either due to the solvent molecules or due to the formation of associated species.^{7,8,9}

The present work was undertaken to investigate the effect of pyridine and ammonia on bis (2-guanidinium benzimidazole) nickel (II) complex salts.

We have prepared bis-(2-guanidinium benzimidazole) nickel(II) complex salts which are rose red, diamagnetic and have square planar structure¹⁰ as shown below:

On thermal study it was found that in the case of the complex iodide only, the compound becomes paramagnetic when heated to 210°. This paramagnetism developed in the solid has been attributed to octahedral configuration with iodide ion interaction forming polymers¹¹.

EXPERIMENTAL

di-pyridino bis-(2-guanidinium benzimidazole nickel (II) sulphate.—bis (2-guanidinium benzimidazole nickel (II) complex salts were prepared as reported by us¹⁰. The complex salts are rose red in colour. The salts were made anhydrous by keeping them in a vacuum desiccator over KOH. The rose red anhydrous sulphate was refluxed with an excess of pure and dry pyridine (B.D.H. pyridine A.R. quality was freshly distilled). After 4 hours refluxing the rose red solid gradually changed over to olive green; the solution also turned pale green. The solid product was filtered and after partial drying in air was kept in a pyridine atmosphere desiccator. This olive green product was also obtained slowly by triturating the anhydrous sulphate with pyridine.

It was found that these pyridine adducts could be also obtained by keeping the different anhydrous complex nickel salts for a sufficiently long time in pyridine atmosphere in a desiccator. In case of complex halides and nitrate adducts produced were thick green liquids and no solid could be isolated.

di-ammine bis-(2-guanidinium benzimidazole nickel (II) salts.—In case of ammonia adducts, the products were obtained by keeping the different anhydrous salts in ammonia atmosphere. The solid products formed were directly used for analysis and magnetic study. Table I shows the analytical results.

7. G. M. Harris, S. L. Lenzler and H. L. Martin, *Ann. J. Chem.*, 1958, 11, 331.
8. D. P. Graddon E. C. Walton, *Nature*, 1961, 190, 906.
9. G. J. Bullen, R. Mason and P. Pauling, *ibid*, 1961, 189, 291.
10. A. K. Banerjee and S. P. Ghosh, *J. Ind. Chem. Sec.*, 1961, 38, 237.
11. S. P. Ghosh and A. K. Banerjee, *J. Inorg. & Nuclear Chem.*, 28 (1), 167,

TABLE I.

	Found%			Calculated %		
	Ni	anion	Py/NH ₃	Ni	anion	Py/NH ₃
<i>bis-pyridine adduct</i>						
[X (Py) ₂]SO ₄	8.75	14.50	23.99	8.88	14.58	23.92
<i>di-ammonia adducts.</i>						
[X (NH ₃) ₂]Cl ₂	11.44	13.78	6.42	11.42	13.82	6.61
[X (NH ₃) ₂]Br ₂	9.65	26.70	5.56	9.77	26.63	5.66
[X (NH ₃) ₂]SO ₄	10.96	17.88	6.28	10.90	17.90	6.31

When left in the atmosphere, these adducts slowly lose pyridine ammonia and change over to the original red rose complexes. Moisture hastens this conversion. The pyridine adducts are found to be more stable than the ammonia adducts when exposed to the atmosphere.

Adducts of both pyridine and ammonia were paramagnetic. Magnetic measurements were done in a Gouy balance at room temperature (303°K), with solid samples, except in the case of the dipyridino complex bromide, which was determined in pyridine solution. The balance was calibrated with Hg[Co(CNS)₄] according to Figgis and Nyholm¹². Table II shows the magnetic moments of these complexes. Diamagnetic corrections quoted have been computed from Pascal's constants.

TABLE II

Compound	$\chi_m \times 10^6$	$\chi_m \times 10^6$	dia. correction $\chi \times 10^6$	$\chi_m \times 10^6$	μ .B.M.
[Ni (C ₆ H ₉ N ₅) ₂ Py ₂]SO ₄	5.24	3462.07	345.9	3807.97	3.05
[Ni (C ₆ H ₉ N ₅) ₂ (NH ₃) ₂]Cl ₂	6.51	3342.20	283.0	3627.20	2.98
[Ni (C ₆ H ₉ N ₅) ₂ (NH ₃) ₂]Br ₂	5.89	3538.10	300.0	3838.10	3.05
[Ni (C ₆ H ₉ N ₅) ₂ (NH ₃) ₂]SO ₄	6.36	3403.40	277.8	3681.20	3.00
[Ni (C ₆ H ₉ N ₅) ₂ Py ₂]Br ₂	4.48	3255.61	368.1	3623.71	2.98

Electronic absorption spectra of bis-(2-guanidinium benzimidazole) nickel (II) complexes in pyridine solution were taken in a Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer with one cm. cell. Electronic absorption spectra in cm⁻¹ and ligand field parameters B and β are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

	³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{2g}	³ A _{2g} → E _g (D)	³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{1g} (F)	³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{1g} (P)	B	β
[X] chloride	10410	12340	16666	29850	1019	0.98
[X] bromide	10640	12190	16666	30000	989	0.94
[X] iodide	10410	12190	17240	29850	1057	1.01
[X] nitrate	10400	12500	16666	29850	1021	0.98
[X] sulphate	10470	12666	16900	30000	1030	0.99

12. B. N. Figgis and R. S. Nyholm, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 4190.

The average ligand field splitting parameter, $\Delta(10Dq)$ calculated from ${}^3A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ transition equals to 10466 cm^{-1} and the average β value is 0.98.

The effective spin orbit coupling parameter, λ within the crystal is calculated from the relation $g = 2 - 8\lambda/10Dq$. If we assume the value of g to be equal to 2.14, the value obtained in case of $[\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_6] \text{Br}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, then λ for these complexes is reduced from the free ion value¹⁴ of -324 cm^{-1} to -180 cm^{-1} .

The Racah parameter, B , was calculated from the diagonal sum rule, $15B = \nu_1 + \nu_2 - 3\Delta$. The nephelauxetic coefficient, β , was given by B/B' where B' is the value of unperturbed gaseous ion. The value of B' was taken to be 1040 cm^{-1} .

DISCUSSION

In case of the pyridine adducts it was possible to isolate dipyridino bis-(2-guanidinium benzimidazole) nickel (II) sulphate only in the solid state. Other pyridino adducts were studied in solution. In case of ammonia solid products were separated but electronic absorption spectra could not be studied as no suitable solvent could be found out. From their stability in air it was found that the dipyridino adduct of the complex sulphate was most stable.

Taking into account the triplet state for octahedral nickel (II) of chromophore NiN_6 type the progression of energy is $\nu_1 = {}^3A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ ($10800-11500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), $\nu_2 = {}^3A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (F) ($16500-18900 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and $\nu_3 = {}^3T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (P) ($27200-29000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$)¹⁶. From the electronic absorption spectra of the pyridine adducts the complexes thus appear to be octahedral with almost Oh symmetry. The spin forbidden ${}^3A_{1g}E_g \rightarrow (D)$ transition could also be observed in these complexes. This has also been observed in case of Lifschitz nickel (II) complexes¹⁷. The higher Dq value for the di-pyridino complex bromide can not be easily understood. This may probably be due to the less electronegative nature of the bromine atom, thereby more negative charge is released to the metal atom and hence enhancing the overlap of the metal t_{2g} orbital.

Generally the reduction of the Racah parameter, B , from its free ion value is taken as evidence of appreciable covalence in the metal ligand bond. The reduction in λ is also attributed to the same cause¹³.

Magnetic moments found for the complexes lie between 2.98—3.05 B.M. This is slightly lower than those found for octahedral nickel (II) complexes ($\mu = 3.2 \text{ B.M.}$) that are regular or have weak axial distortion. The lower value may be due to the increase in the axial distortion.

13. J. Owen, *Proc., Roy. Soc. London*, 1955, A 227, 183.

14. C. J. Ballhausen, "Introduction to Ligand field theory", Mc Graw-Hill, 129, 1962.

15. C. K. Jorgensen, "Absorption spectra & chemical binding in complex", 1962, 136.

16. C. K. Jorgensen, "Absorption spectra & chemical binding in complexes", 1962, 296.

17. W.C.E. Higginson, S.C. Nyburg and J. S. Wood, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, 3, 463.

Octahedral environment in these complexes is supported by both magnetic and electronic absorption studies. From spectral data considerable covalency in the metal ligand bonding is also suggested. Reaction with pyridine and ammonia can be described by :

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